

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

**EMPOWERING CREATIVITY AND
INNOVATION IN EDUCATION:
A STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR THE
INTEGRATION OF ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE.**

Carlos Filipe Da Silva Costa

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Policy Statement

The strategic integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into educational systems is paramount to leveraging the advancements of the digital age and fostering a creative and innovative learning environment. This policy brief advocates for developing and implementing comprehensive frameworks to guide the ethical and practical use of AI in education, emphasizing the enhancement of creativity among students while mitigating potential dependencies on technology.

Background

The global landscape is at a pivotal juncture. Recent AI improvements and capabilities have led to its adoption in all sectors of human activity, and education is no exception.

Since the 2010s, AI has been evolving at a considerably fast pace. First, advancements in Deep Learning have led to improvements in image and speech recognition, language translation, and autonomous systems. Thus, Natural Language Processing (NLP) benefited from these advancements. NLPs enable computers to understand, interpret, and use human language. Then, in 2014, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) revolutionized how machines can generate realistic images, videos, and even music. Things accelerated in 2017 with the "Attention Is All You Need" paper by Vaswani et al. (2017), which improved NLP by enabling more effective handling of sequential data. Another step forward came with the introduction of Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers (BERT) by Google in 2019 (Jacob et al., 2019). BERT set new standards for NLP tasks, including question answering and language inference, by understanding the context of words in sentences more effectively. Subsequently, the Generative Pre-trained Transformer came out by OpenAI. The GPTs series use Large Language Models (LLM). Earlier NLP models and techniques often relied on rule-based systems and smaller-scale machine-learning models that required extensive feature engineering. LLMs, with their ability to learn from large datasets, have reduced the need for manual rule-setting and feature engineering, allowing for more nuanced understanding and generation of language. However, this dependency on data introduced the risk of bias.

Most LLMs, including those in the GPT series, can process sequences of words and understand the context of each word within a sentence or paragraph. Given a prompt,

LLMs can then generate coherent and contextually relevant text that is difficult to distinguish from that created by humans. So, for instance, they can answer questions, summarise texts, and translate languages, and with additional tools and a simple prompt, they can generate code, images, and other media. AI's capabilities, especially in creative domains, have expanded dramatically. It can also solve problems; GPT-3.5 had some difficulties with certain basic mathematical concepts, but GPT-4 significantly improved (OpenAI, 2023). The incorporation of the Wolfram plug-in has nearly erased the remaining limitations (Bailey, 2023; Wolfram, 2023). Considering the rapid pace, we can infer a near future where AI's cognitive competencies could parallel those of humans.

AI introduction at school and its risks

The educational sector stands at the forefront of a technological revolution, with AI, particularly LLMs, playing a pivotal role in reshaping pedagogical methods. Previous technologies did not change dramatically the way we study; they allowed access to content and resources (Kulesza, 2011), but AI is bringing new possibilities. According to Bailey (2023), AI transforms education by enhancing learning experiences and offering personalized support. Here's how:

- AI can simulate human-like conversations to offer adaptive tutoring, helping students understand complex concepts and improve their writing skills. It encourages deeper inquiry into learning subjects and can be particularly beneficial for students with disabilities or those with foreign languages. AI could not only assist in learning but also facilitate new creative expression.
- For teachers, AI can take over routine tasks such as drafting lesson plans, creating quizzes, and generating diverse instructional materials, freeing up time for more direct student engagement. It also provides insights and recommendations to address individual student needs, tailoring teaching, and supports teachers in reflecting on and improving their instructional methods.
- AI helps parents, students, and teachers with administrative tasks.

Despite AI's vast educational potential, its adoption among teachers remains limited. However, usage is expected to grow as AI capabilities become integrated into familiar platforms and tools. Innovations in AI, tailored specifically for educational contexts,

are poised to enrich teaching and learning experiences further.

It's crucial to emphasize the necessity of meticulous integration that supports effective instructional strategies and cultivates innovative teaching and learning methods. Similar to the incorporation of various technologies, embedding AI within the educational framework presents a set of challenges or concerns (Bailey, 2023, Education Now, 2021):

- Cheating among students is widespread across educational institutions, from schools to colleges and universities. The advent of technology has made it simpler to complete assignments like essays without conducting thorough research. Educators are aware that outsourcing work, whether to friends or relatives, is a classic technique. Although one might detect differences in writing style, the core issue is the growing prevalence of cheating. The widespread availability of free AI tools, accessible to anyone with an internet connection, exacerbates this problem, making it easier for students to cheat and challenging for institutions to maintain academic standards.
- Bias in AI algorithms, particularly in large language models (LLMs), is a significant issue because these models are trained on vast datasets that may contain societal biases. OpenAI has taken steps to address this by diversifying the training data to include a broad range of sources, aiming to reduce bias from any single type of content. Continuous monitoring and analysis of the model's outputs are essential for spotting and correcting biases. These efforts are crucial to avoid reinforcing existing societal biases. Involving human reviewers in the development process and incorporating user feedback are vital strategies to improve the models. Techniques like differential privacy, fairness constraints, and adversarial training are also used to further minimize biases in the outputs, leading to fairer and more reliable AI systems. The development process should also be ethical and transparent, with open research to allow external feedback.
- Privacy concerns with generative AI arise as students' and educators' interactions, results, and personal data could be stored and analyzed, potentially compromising their privacy. Educators must avoid entering or revealing sensitive information about themselves, their peers, or their students. In the EU, personal information is regulated by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU), 2016), which requires that any personal data used by generative

AI systems must be processed lawfully, transparently, and precisely. Additionally, individuals have rights over their data, including access, rectification, and deletion.

- Wrong results from generative AI pose significant concerns, as they are often presented convincingly, making all answers appear legitimate despite disclaimers. Users are thus required to verify AI-generated outcomes carefully. Although technological advancements are expected to reduce the risk of inaccuracies and biases.
- Social concerns as students may not interact or share with their pairs.

The challenges and concerns mentioned above are not limited to AI; similar issues have been encountered with previous technologies, already leading to the implementation of various policies. However, a distinct risk associated with AI, amplified by its advanced capabilities and novel forms of interaction, warrants special attention. Over-reliance on technology, particularly AI, highlights the potential erosion of critical thinking and problem-solving skills among students. This issue is exacerbated by AI's ability to provide rapid and often accurate responses, which may encourage students to become passive recipients of information rather than active participants in the learning process, engaging in critical analysis and problem-solving. This focus on over-reliance hides another problem that can be formulated as AI's impact on students' creativity.

Generative AI and creativity

Creativity, a cornerstone of student development, necessitates a holistic approach encompassing critical thinking, conative abilities, and imaginative capacities. As AI becomes more embedded in educational practices, understanding its impact on these aspects of creativity is paramount.

Creativity in education is multifaceted, involving the ability to generate novel and valuable ideas (critical thinking and imaginative capacities) and the motivation and perseverance to bring these ideas to fruition (conative skills). The conative aspect of creativity, often overlooked, involves the personal drive, effort, and action-oriented behaviors crucial for creative endeavors. It is this aspect that propels individuals to pursue and navigate these challenges and fully harness AI's potential in education; it is essential to develop a nuanced understanding of how AI,

particularly, LLMs can be integrated into educational frameworks to support and enhance the creative process without undermining the development of intrinsic creative skills and constructive efforts among students.

The future capabilities of LLMs extend beyond mere content generation, offering possibilities for creating dynamic, interactive learning environments that adapt to individual students' needs and foster collaborative learning experiences. These environments could stimulate creativity by presenting challenges, scenarios, and problems tailored to students' learning levels and interests, encouraging deeper engagement and exploration.

To ensure that AI acts as a catalyst for creativity rather than a crutch, educational strategies must emphasize the development of students' conative abilities. This involves teaching students how to use AI tools critically and creatively, encouraging them to question, modify, and extend the AI-generated content, and fostering an environment where persistence, experimentation, and risk-taking are valued components of the learning process.

Moreover, as AI continues to evolve, so will its role in education. Staying ahead of this curve requires ongoing research, professional development for educators, and adaptive policies that can accommodate the rapid pace of technological change while preserving the core values of education. By doing so, we can prepare students not just to thrive in a world where AI is ubiquitous but also to shape the future of AI itself, using their creativity and conative skills to direct these technologies towards positive and ethical applications.

Findings

The introduction of AI in education presents a dual-edged sword concerning creativity. On one hand, AI, particularly generative AI, offers tools that can significantly enhance creative processes, providing students with novel means of expression and problem-solving. On the other hand, there is a growing concern that reliance on AI for creative tasks might hinder students' ability to develop independent creative skills, leading to dependency. The conative aspect of creativity, which involves motivation, effort, and perseverance in the creative process, is particularly at risk.

The effective integration of AI into education depends on strong political commitment and robust institutional frameworks. To fully realize the educational benefits of Generative AI, it is essential to formulate and implement well-considered policies. Striking the right balance is critical: we must harness AI to boost students' creative potential while vigilantly avoiding over-reliance that could lead to dependency.

This calls for a closer examination of the roles and approaches of key players, including UNESCO, the United States, and the European Union, in shaping the future of AI in education. China is also a significant actor, but official Chinese sources are more difficult to find.

UNESCO

UNESCO recognizes AI's potential to revolutionize education, addressing significant challenges and advancing towards Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4). Thus, UNESCO supports using AI in education, but it also recognizes that the rapid AI advancements bring risks, outpacing policy and regulatory development. As UNESCO (2023a) highlighted, the slow adoption of comprehensive AI frameworks reflects global caution with long-term implications. For this purpose, a series of recommendations are made in the Education 2030 Agenda (UNESCO, 2020), which stemmed from the Beijing Consensus (UNESCO, 2019).

The Beijing Consensus participants included "50 government ministers and vice ministers, as well as around 500 international representatives from more than 100 Member States, United Nations agencies, academic institutions, civil society and the private sector".

The recommendations cover AI integration in education policies, investments, education management, ensuring equitable AI use, and ethical AI practices. In summary, it advocates a human-centered AI approach, emphasizing inclusion and equity, reducing inequalities in knowledge access, and preventing technological divides. The goal is to ensure equitable benefits from AI advancements for all.

UNESCO also published a comprehensive "Guidance for Generative AI in Education and Research" (UNESCO, 2023b), which aims to prepare institutions and individuals for AI's impact on education, fostering a shared understanding of its opportunities and challenges and the competencies required in the AI era. The text, with the same central precepts as the agenda, goes behind the risks mentioned previously and is more detailed. It presents potential uses:

"Generative AI for research, to facilitate teaching, as a 1:1 coach for the self-paced acquisition of foundational skills, to enable inquiry or project-based learning, and to support learners with special needs. For each use, advantages, risks, and implementations are analyzed.

The document addresses concerns about creativity in two sections: "Review and address the long-term impacts: Over time, relying on GenAI tools or content in education may profoundly affect the development of human capacities such as critical thinking skills and creativity. These potential effects should be evaluated and addressed," and "Without proper pedagogical strategies to stimulate learners' intrinsic motivations, it may limit children's creativity and originality, leading to formulaic writing." While it underscores the need for further investigation, the discussion primarily situates the safeguarding of creativity within the scope of pedagogical approaches.

US Department of Education

The Office of Educational Technology published the "Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Teaching and Learning; Insights and Recommendations" (U.S. Department of Education, 2023). It describes the risks and opportunities posed by AI. The text is oriented as a series of questions that one should ask oneself before implementing AI tools in a way that minimizes the potential harms of AI while maximizing the benefits. It looks at the balance between advancements and "classical" class experience and stresses the importance of keeping "humans in the loop"; AI cannot "replace a teacher." But its recommendations amount to guidance at best. They point out that the innovation pace in AI is outpacing many policymakers' understanding.

There is no direct mention of the question of creativity, only a more general question: "Is high-quality research or evaluations about the impacts of using the AI system for student learning available?"

European Union

The AI panorama in the EU is structured by different texts: the White Paper on AI (European Commission, 2020) setting the AI vision for Europe, the proposal for an AI Act (European Commission, 2021), and a new Coordinated Plan with Member States (European Commission, 2020a). The Digital Education Action Plan 2021-2027 lists the priorities and strategies for implementing digital education (European Commission, 2020b).

The commissioner for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education, and Youth, Mariya Gabriel, said: "Artificial Intelligence has a great potential to transform education and training for students, teachers, and school staff. It can help students with learning difficulties and support teachers through individualized learning. But using AI and data comes with privacy, security, and safety risks, especially involving young people. Therefore, I am pleased that these Guidelines will help ensure that these risks are being considered and our children can be kept safe and protected." (European Commission, 2022).

In the text "Artificial Intelligence And Education: A Critical View through the Lens of Human Rights, democracy, and the Rule of Law, by the Council of Europe (Holmes et al. 2022), the problem of AI's impact on creativity is mentioned in a few paragraphs. First, for education, it is clearly stated that the desired competencies are "(how learners approach complex challenges): critical thinking/problem-solving, creativity, communication, and collaboration." Then, in "AI applications and pedagogy," most applications or solutions are criticized as they are based on behaviorism, thus implying conditional learning where the machine gives feedback, for instance, right/wrong, and the learner assimilates the subject but does not necessarily understand it. Critical thinking is missing. One last mention appears in the section "AI applications and emotion," where the impact on the learner of certain AI technologies is questioned.

These texts also mention critical thinking, which is part of creativity, but this still needs to be encompassed clearly as it should be.

All previous texts identify AI's potential risk to student creativity but do not offer a solution. Policymakers consider this issue to be primarily pedagogical. However, there is an opportunity for policy measures to guide and enhance AI integration, thus creating a more favorable educational environment that promotes creativity.

Recommendations

- *Promote Digital Literacy and AI Education:* Integrate digital literacy and AI education into curricula to prepare students for a future where AI is everywhere. This includes teaching students about the workings of AI, its potential biases, and ethical considerations, empowering them to engage with AI technologies;

- *Foster Collaboration Between Technologists and Educators:* Encourage partnerships between AI developers, educators, and pedagogical experts to ensure that AI tools are designed with educational needs and principles in mind. Such collaboration can create AI applications that genuinely enhance learning and creativity.
- *Invest in Research and Development:* Allocate funding for research and development in educational AI to explore innovative applications, assess their impact on learning outcomes and creativity, and identify best practices for integrating into teaching and learning processes. Provide training for educators to use AI tools effectively.
- *Implement Adaptive Learning Technologies:* Support adopting adaptive learning technologies that can personalize education, catering to individual students' needs, learning styles, and paces. This approach can maximize the potential of AI to enhance learning outcomes while fostering creativity and critical thinking.

Policies should be crafted to incubate the principles of Artificial Intelligence, ensuring they are adaptable enough to accommodate the rapid pace of technological development while also considering the impact of AI on students. These policies must lay the groundwork for an educational ecosystem responsive to AI technologies' evolving capabilities, ensuring they enhance rather than hinder the academic experience: creativity and well-being.

Conclusions

As we navigate the integration of AI into educational landscapes, it is crucial for policies to strike a balance between specificity and generality to remain effective amidst rapid technological change. Policymakers play a pivotal role in shaping an educational environment where AI catalyzes innovation, inclusivity, and lifelong learning. By implementing these forward-looking recommendations, we can ensure that the academic sector keeps pace with AI developments and harnesses them to enhance learning experiences, foster creativity, and prepare students for a future where AI plays a central role.

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Carlos Filipe Da Silva Costa (InterAgency Institute): PhD in physics and Master in Strategic Protection of the Country's System (Società Italiana per l'Organizzazione Internazionale); Research Affiliate at InterAgency Institute.

InterAgency Institute

<https://interagency.institute/>
contact@interagency.institute

Editor-in-chief: Larlecianne Piccolli